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STUDENT SPEECH CONTEST CANDIDATE X

ORAL PRESENTATION X

ARC-JET TESTING OF ULTRA-HIGH-TEMPERATURE CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

In the framework of the Horizon 2020 project C³HARME, focused on the development of new-class Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites for near-zero ablation Aerospace Thermal Protection Systems, an experimental campaign has been carried out in the arc-jet wind tunnel available at the University of Naples “Federico II”. Different formulations of ZrB₂-based composites with carbon fibers were characterized in an aero-thermo-chemical environment representative of atmospheric re-entry, exposing small specimens to a supersonic flow of simulated air, at specific total enthalpies up to 20 MJ/kg, in presence of a considerable amount of dissociated chemical species. Mass and thickness measurements before and after testing allowed for the estimation of ablation rates of the analyzed materials, which demonstrated a good performance, although with some mechanical resistance issues. Non-intrusive infrared equipment (pyrometers and a thermo-camera) was employed to monitor surface temperatures, and during most of the tests a spontaneous temperature jump of several hundred degrees was observed, with maximum temperature values over 2800 K. Computational Fluid Dynamic simulations made possible rebuilding the thermo-fluid-dynamic and chemical flow field around the samples, and proposing a preliminary interpretation for the temperature jump, based on a twofold mechanism: an increased catalytic activity and a dramatic reduction of the thermal conductivity of the oxide layers forming on the exposed part of the sample. The oxide phases demonstrated however the ability to preserve the unoxidized bulk materials at reasonable temperatures.

Keywords: Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites; Arc-jet wind tunnel testing; Near-zero ablation; Computational Fluid Dynamic simulation; Temperature Jump.

Introduction

Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramics (UHTC), based on transition metals carbides and diborides, are appealing as materials for Thermal Protection Systems (TPS) of hypersonic vehicles, which have to withstand extremely demanding aero-thermo-dynamic and chemical conditions [1,2], essentially due to their ability to survive extremely high temperatures [3]. UHTCs however need the introduction of secondary phases to improve their properties, such as SiC [4], to provide them with better oxidation resistance [5], or carbon fibers, to upgrade the mechanical performance [6], leading to the definition of Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites (UHTCMC). In this framework, the Horizon 2020 European C³HARME research project is focused on a new class of UHTCMCs for near zero-ablation thermal protection systems [7]. An experimental characterization campaign is currently ongoing in the arc-jet wind tunnel available at the University of Naples "Federico II" (UNINA), where small samples are exposed to atmospheric re-entry simulated environment at maximum flow total enthalpies up to 20 MJ/kg, monitoring their surface temperatures by non-intrusive diagnostic equipment and evaluating the ablation rates at those demanding conditions. The experimental activities are supported by Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations, which help rebuilding both the thermo-fluid-dynamic flow field around the test articles and the thermal behavior of the materials samples.

Test setup and numerical models

Experimental setup

Experimental tests were carried out in the arc-jet wind tunnel available at the University of Naples "Federico II", named SPES (Small Planetary Entry Simulator). This is an open circuit, continuous blow-down wind tunnel where a nitrogen plasma (0.8 g/s) is generated by an industrial torch and mixed to a secondary cold oxygen flow (0.2 g/s), to simulate earth atmospheric composition. A converging-diverging nozzle is employed to expand the hot mixture to a nominal supersonic Mach number equal to 3. A detailed facility description can be found in [8]. Small sized material samples (Fig. 1) were placed in front of nozzle exit section, at a distance of 1 cm, by a thermally protected supporting mechanism.

Fig. 1 Nominal design of UHTCMC samples. Dimensions in mm.

During the test, the arc power of the plasma torch and consequently the total enthalpy of the flow were gradually increased through successive increments, leading correspondingly to an increase in pressure and temperature. The total specific enthalpy (H_0) is obtained through an energy balance at the exit of the plasma torch, based on measurement of temperature and flow rate of cooling water [8] and the values corresponding to each torch arc power step are reported in Table 1. The surface temperature of the samples was continuously measured by digital two-color pyrometers (Infratherm ISQ5 and IGAR6, Impac Electronic GmbH, Germany) at an acquisition rate of 100 Hz. In addition, an infrared (IR) thermo-camera (TC, Pyroview 512N, DIAS Infrared GmbH, Germany) allows for the evaluation of the temperature distribution over the sample surface. The procedure employed to set the correct value of spectral emittance, on which the IR-TC measurement is dependent, is reported in [8].

Table 1. Specific total enthalpies at different steps during the tests.

Step	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
H_0 [MJ/kg]	5.5	7.0	8.5	10	12	14	16	18	20

Numerical models

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations were performed to characterize the flow field inside the facility and to rebuild the thermal behavior of the samples. The steady-state formulation of Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations is solved in an axisymmetric domain including mixing chamber, nozzle and test chamber, for a turbulent multi-reacting gas mixture with five species (i.e. O, O₂, NO, N and N₂), in chemical non-equilibrium. Finite rate chemical reactions are considered. The temperature field inside the sample and its supporting elements is computed solving the energy equation and setting a thermal coupling condition on the interfaces between fluid and solid domains (temperature and heat flux continuities). Particular focus is given to the effect of surface catalycity, which is defined as the ability of the material surface to promote exothermal recombination reactions at the wall. The catalytic recombination coefficient γ_w [9] (not catalytic: $\gamma_w = 0$; fully catalytic: $\gamma_w = 1$), which affects the heat flux on the sample, is computed by extracting the related quantities from the fluid field solution.

Results and discussion

Eight samples were tested, all based on a ZrB_2 -SiC matrix, with different carbon fibers architectures: two samples had coated long carbon fibers, with matrix/fibers volume ratio of 50/50%, and were sintered by hot pressing (HP-CLF-1 and HP-CLF-2); two samples had uncoated long fibers, with matrix/fibers volume ratio of 60/40%, and were sintered by hot pressing (HP-ULF-1 and HP-ULF-2); two samples had uncoated short fibers, with matrix/fibers volume ratio of 60/40%, and were sintered by spark plasma sintering (SPS-SF-1 and SPS-SF-2); finally, two samples had uncoated short fibers, with matrix/fibers volume ratio of 60/40%, and were sintered by hot pressing (HP-SF-1 and HP-SF-2). Mass and thickness measurements before and after tests allowed for an estimation of the ablation rates.

Sample HP-CLF-1 was tested three times, since the first were preliminary tests, at low specific total enthalpy levels, to check the setup and assess the ability of such materials to withstand the demanding conditions. Thermal histories of the samples are reported in Fig. 2. Samples HP-ULF-1, HP-ULF-2, SPS-SF-2 and HP-SF-1 were tested up to the specific total enthalpy level corresponding to step 7 of Table 1. Samples HP-CLF-1 and HP-CLF-2 reached a temperature above 2400 K when exposed to the maximum specific total enthalpy level, whereas all the others samples, on the contrary, exceeded 2700 K and in some cases even 2800 K. In particular, for most of them it was clear that a sudden rise in temperature (“temperature jump”) of several hundred degrees occurred during the last step, even at a constant arc power, after a steady state condition had apparently been reached.

Fig. 2 Temperature histories of the samples, measured by the ISQ5 pyrometer.

After the tests, all the samples heads appeared completely oxidized, with a white layer, probably mainly composed of ZrO_2 , covering the surface (Fig. 3). This layer was fragile and showed a tendency to spall off from samples HP-CLF-1 and HP-CLF-2, and it completely detached from SPS-SF-1 and SPS-SF-2, whereas all the other samples preserved the original shape and a perfect structural integrity, with a slight thickening due to the formation of the outer oxide. Anyway, the ablation rates of all the samples was on the order of 10^{-3} - 10^{-4} mm/s, which makes them promising for the final application.

Fig. 3. Sample HP-SF-2 (a) before and (b) after the test.

CFD simulations were carried out to provide an interpretation for the phenomenon of the temperature jump, taking as reference the last step of the test on sample HP-ULF-2. The flow field inside mixing chamber, supersonic nozzle and test chamber was simulated employing the numerical model described above. The most interesting information retrieved was that, around the samples, a considerable amount of dissociated oxygen and nitrogen is present (with mass fractions around 0.2 and 0.3 respectively), making the contribution of surface catalycity crucial for the determination of the heat flux. The thermal behavior of the sample was simulated by matching the temperature axial profiles estimated by the IR-TC before and after temperature jump. It is interesting to notice that the jump seems to occur only on the front surface of the sample (Fig. 4(a)). This phenomenon could be associated to the formation of zirconia on the outer face of the sample, upon complete removal of the protective borosilicate glass forming at lower temperatures [10], possibly leading to a twofold mechanism: increase in catalytic efficiency and dramatic reduction of thermal conductivity in the porous oxidized phase. To match numerical and experimental profiles (Fig. 4(b)), the thermal conductivity of the unoxidized bulk was set to 40 W/m·K, the oxide thickness and thermal conductivity were 800 μm and 2 W/m·K respectively, the surface emissivity 0.5 and the catalytic efficiency γ_w $2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ before the jump and $1 \cdot 10^{-1}$ after the jump.

Fig. 4. (a) Thermographic images of sample HP-ULF-2 before and after temperature jump and (b) comparison between numerical and experimental temperature axial profiles.

Conclusions

Eight UHTCMC samples based on $\text{ZrB}_2\text{-SiC}$ matrix and different carbon fibers architectures were tested in a supersonic arc-jet wind tunnel at specific total enthalpies up to 20 MJ/kg. Temperatures over 2800 K were reached, associated to a temperature jump of several hundred degrees for most of the samples. This phenomenon was interpreted, based on the outcomes of CFD simulations, as depending on increased catalytic activity and reduced thermal conductivity of the front part of the samples, related to the formation of a ZrO_2 layer, which however shelters the rear region, which reaches more reasonable temperatures. Ablation rates were low ($10^{-3}\text{-}10^{-4}$ mm/s), making these materials promising for a near-zero ablation TPS application.

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